

Teaching Methods as a Predictor on Promoting STEM Education: A Domain Specific Focus on National Curriculum Document 2006

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Abstract

Teaching is prophecy and sophisticated profession. It is carried out through nation builders and key figures of societies; Teachers, who zealously knock on students minds, trigger off students' creative and independent thoughts, promptly indulge themselves towards students' fast tracking career and regularly extend beyond academics. They enthusiastically impart instructions and disseminate pedagogical and content knowledge among students to fulfill the deficiency of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics; STEM education. Teachers are sole supplier of knowledge, surrogate parents, mentor, productively, navigate the curriculum and make maximum use of broader techniques; teaching methods to master students in STEM education focusing national curriculum document 2006. National curriculum is an official representative document that concentrates on students' learning outcomes, teaching methods, students' assessment procedures, instructional materials and STEM related competencies. The current research is an attempt to measure the effect of curriculum based pedagogical approaches, use to promote the deficiency of STEM education. The researchers structured current quantitative ex-post-facto research leading to positivist paradigm in district Lahore, on randomly selected sample of 1,152 respondents. After ensuring ethical considerations, the validity and Cronbach's Alpha reliability; .895 of the instrument, the researchers administered self-constructed questionnaires to collect the data from the participants. The results of regression analysis show that teachers were making 51.30% use of curriculum based teaching methods to cultivate STEM education. Furthermore, teachers use of lecture method was good predictor on nurturing STEM education while, problem solving was least predictor in this regards. Moreover, proper implementation of curriculum is a weak feature in Pakistan. On the basis of results, it is recommended that Government of the Punjab and Quaid-i-Azam academy for educational development, may professionally trained primary schools teachers on national curriculum document based teaching methods to promote STEM education.

Introduction

Provisions of individual's education and his/her complete improvement have been remaining foremost goal of educational systems that have strong roots in teaching. Teaching is a multifaceted process. It is a medium of transferring ideas, value and concept to bring positive change in students' behavior during teaching (Mang & Mankilik, 2002) and a path of experience and organization of curricula for students learning (Damar et al., 2016). Teachers use teaching methods to fulfill students need for asking teachers' queries/questions then students' interpretation in unique and constructive ways (Collins & Robert, 2004). Teachers fascinate students by using teaching methods to change students' behavior (Vennix et al., 2018), and educational achievements (Hassan & Akbar, 2020). Teaching methods are multifaceted concept which means the methods and the practices applied by the teacher(s) in domain specific situations to nurture learners' educational success. They are best tool that bring required modifications among students towards desire subject matter (Adunola, 2011). They refer to teachers' strategies used to achieve educational objectives in account of instructional approaches and procedure, teaching course applying teaching material and resources. Teaching methods increase students' effective content understanding, learning and problem solving abilities (Omwirhiren & Ibrahim, 2016), teachers' tactics that are used in classroom to achieve instructional objectives (Najafipour & Jafari, 2013), sum of teachers' approaches, techniques and strategies to encourage students' effective learning (Umer & Siddiqui, 2013), enhance mental processes (Ameh & Dantani, 2012), arouse students' learning desires towards educational needs (Ayeni, 2011) and enhance students motor and sensory growth (Ganyaupfu, 2013). Teachers use as per nature of content and students learning outcomes for higher order learning (Khani, 2003).

Stakeholders are confident that teaching methods are the best appetizer that are used to achieve goals and are effective means for students' success (Motamedi, 2005). Continuous usage of teaching methods access to obtain assign educational goals (Motamedi, 2005; Rizi et al., 2013). Lecture, discussion, demonstration, question answer, brainstorming, inquiry, problem solving and cooperative teaching methods are stated in national curriculum document 2006 (Government of Pakistan, 2006; Nawaz, 2020). Teachers use to enhance Scientific, Technological, Educational and Mathematical; STEM fluency among students (Government of Pakistan, 2010; Hassan, 2020). National curriculum briefly states application of teaching methods for students' better educational needs (Government of Pakistan, 2006) focusing science technology, engineering and mathematical demands.

Lecture is broadly accepted common method of imparting instructions through oral presentation of concepts and thoughts (Feynman, 2005; Harman & Bich, 2010) that demands less time and efforts to instruct information proficiently for content delivery (Marilla & McKeachie, 2011). Learners thoroughly remain passive in classroom and just obtain information from teachers (Umoren & Ogbodo, 2001). Teachers convey plethora of information using lecture method on different topics to make students active during teaching learning process for better achievements (McKeachie & Svinicki, 2006). *Discussion* arouses students' power of ideas sharing with peers (Ndirangu & Udoto, 2011). Students discuss their bookish and content knowledge, provide their opinions and identify their weakness by discussion method (Nilson, 2016). Teachers used this method for sharing of ideas, students conceptual understanding, provoke students' mental abilities and enhance students critical thinking and problem solving skills towards literary contribution (Rahman et al., 2011). *Demonstration* constructs solid concepts on students understanding (Sefton, 2001), clutches students' fundamental scientific ideas, overcomes hurdle in students' misconceptions and effect on students' success (Roth et al., 1997). Demonstration used to provoke, help and produce students' interests towards learning (Crouch et al., 2004) and encourages students' thought provoking process (Njoroge et al., 2014). Teachers used to enhance students' mental growth to arouse innovative ideas regarding daily instructions conducted in classroom (Rotenberg, 2005). They used to probe students' competencies and potential abilities. When teachers ask questions from students during class, this method identifies students' appropriate content and pedagogical knowledge (Duncan & McKeachie, 2005).

Brainstorming provokes students' creative and problem solving skills (Al-Khatib, 2012) and arouses students' devotions towards learning, produces different ideas regarding concerned topics and produces numerous logical concepts to resolve unambiguous problems (Filgona et al., 2016). Teachers ignite students' minds towards appropriate functioning of issues for clarification (Odoh, 2013). Strategy brings positive improvements in students' success in different educational streams towards conceptual understandings (Sabet & Ghorbanpour, 2014). *Inquiry* arouses students' curiosity towards realm of intellectualities and topic understandings. It stimulates students' knowledge construction from direct revelation of evidences (Huzyak-Clark et al., 2007). Teachers act as appetizer towards exploration of universe, discovery of facts, reflection, thinking and critical analysis (Santrock, 2001). *Problem solving* avoids students from rote learning (Kumar, 2003). It enhances students' thoughts towards course, enhances understanding level, boosts confidence, better academic performance in exams, stimulate students towards varieties of learning and support group tasks (Goodnough & Cashion, 2006). Method makes students vigilant and enhances their content base clear understanding (Koray & Koray, 2013). It expands concrete concepts on different topics and gradually pulls down students' habit of learning by heart (Kumar, 2003). Teachers use to enhance students' interpersonal abilities, make students critical thinker, facts searcher, good communicator and team worker (Sungur et al., 2006). Problem solving is considered affective means of arousing students' cognitive abilities (Wilder, 2015). *Cooperative teaching* is teachers' sound acknowledged instructional practices that make students' active information seeker, group contributor, strengthen student teacher relationships and increases their academic achievements (Rojas-Drummond et al., 1998). Teachers actively involves students in teaching learning (Gillies & Boyle, 2010), makes students vigilant (Abrami et al., 2004) effective learner in group as compare to loneliness (Banerjee & Vidyapati, 1997). Teachers used to memorize students' knowledge that lead towards: their intellectual justification, philosophical thoughts, topics understanding, misunderstandings and explanation of information (Winston, 2002)

Concept of STEM education is emerging among Pakistani teachers. They promote and nurture students' awareness on burning educational disciples; STEM education (Hali et al., 2021). Resultantly, implementation of innovative and curriculum based approaches enable students to promote keen interests in aforementioned disciplines, consequently generate further restructured workforce (Ullah et al., 2020). STEM education is constructed on curriculum based thoughts used to master students in the disciplines of science, technology, engineering and mathematics integrating interdisciplinary and applied approaches (Shaikh et al., 2019). Trials and benefits of universalization and conscious based prudence are strongly affecting on the worth of educational institutions. Scientific innovations are reaching door step of every individual (Parveen & Tran, 2020). Pakistani upcoming learners are indulged in scientific and digital world (Afridi et al., 2020). Applications of STEM education arouse students' hidden potentials and polish skills in promoting their capabilities and

beyond (Hammad, 2020). Teachers are playing their immense responsibilities in imparting instructions to promote STEM education focusing cohesive knowledge patterns exemplifying real-world applications (Farooqi, 2022; Mustafa et al., 2022).

STEM education in Pakistani educational institutions is spreading day by day. Government of Pakistan is taking pain in this regard. Investing of money is key indicators that launch the widespread education to cope with international standards. Huge amount of 3-billion Pakistani rupees invested to promote the applications of STEM and digital education throughout the state. Initial purpose of this project is to students' cognitive abilities towards STEM education that is going to become history in the field of STEM education. With the help of stakeholders, Government abstracted 464 educational institution throughout the state that will entitled as "STEM schools" to cope the thirst of STEM education; important way to secure bright future of state (Shaikh et al., 2019). Government of Pakistan holds 5,000 buildings of public sector schools that will be upgraded in STEM/Digital education for future of Pakistani students. Renowned educational institution "Pakistan Science Foundation" is also currently working on various STEM related projects and more programs will be launch soon (Farooqi, 2022). Although Pakistan is currently suffer in financial, political, religious, cultural, health Covid-19 and educational crises, but Government of Pakistan taking voluntarily decisions to overcome the deficiency of STEM education in this regards (Anwar, 2017). With the collaboration of public-private partnership dilemmas occurring in spreading STEM educations are overwhelmed momentarily (Malik, 2017).

National Curriculum document, 2006 is a dynamic source that meets ever changing realities and provides equal opportunities for learning without class favoritism (Government of Pakistan, 2006; Mahmood, 2010). It raises quality of education provided through set standards for educational inputs, processes, outputs and institutionalizing the process of monitoring and evaluation from the lowest to the highest levels (Government of Pakistan, 2014). Applications and identifications of teaching methods and aligning the overall curriculum with self-efficacious and behavioral attributes, which are beneficial for classroom management, allowing students to access information to increase their academic confidence (Government of Pakistan, 2017). National curriculum document, 2006 emphasizes to apply teachers' choices and decisions in classrooms focusing their confidence, classroom management potentials and pedagogical approaches (Government of Pakistan, 2006) for implementing STEM education. Teachers have diversities in their classroom activities (Zimmerman, 2013) on the basis of students STEM related skills. Teaching methods are practiced, as mentioned in curriculum, according to the needs of the students in classrooms for students better STEM nurturing (Government of Pakistan, 2014; Nawaz, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

School is a unique place having small cultural diversity which effects on teachers and students. Teachers are nation builders and have concern towards students' success. They made efforts to pursue for students' better education. In public sector schools education is going to be turn down gradually (Adu et al., 2012) especially in STEM education. Teachers deal students having different class size, students nature like fairness/unfairness; honest/dishonest; regular/absconder; intelligent/dull and; active/tedious. These are key constructs that directly affects teachers' teaching methods, used to implement STEM education. Teachers make less used of national curriculum document based teaching methods among students to implement STEM education. Resultantly, students become mind-numbing, dull, less cooperative in class (Umer & Siddiqui, 2013) and apparently fruitless for educational improvement (McGee & Howard, 1998). Teaching methods boosts students' abilities; make them active in class, create potential to solve practical problems and improve their understanding level (Boud & Feletti, 1997). Teachers use teaching methods in class room for students' better understanding (Cousins & Walker, 2000). Stakeholders making constant complaints regarding educational standards in public sector educational institutions are going to decline due to students' poor attainments (Adu et al., 2012). Teaching methods are best predictors that significantly effects on students' achievements (Tella & Tella, 2003). It is one of the factors that teachers are not portraying their attributes with true spirit in their classrooms with vigor which result in implementing poor STEM education. Resultantly, education remains deprived and is going to bleak gradually (Adu et al., 2012) in public sector schools of Punjab. Public schools students show poor annual results aptly depict constant decline from last few years (Andrabi et al., 2012). This continuous declining level of public sector students' poor fallout is due to teachers' slackness (Kitti, 2014). Teaching methods are considered deep rooted and widespread attributes which have significant effects on promoting STEM education (Cassidy & Eachus, 2000; Adeyemo, 2005; Akomolafe, 2010). Pakistani schools teachers poorly followed guidelines stated in national curriculum document (Nawaz, 2020; Nawaz & Akbar, 2021). Curriculum has elusive, mysterious, confusing, and fragmentary characteristics (Aubusson & Watson, 1999; Ornstein & Hunkins, 2014) that is less implement with vigor and spirit. Teaching learning material for teachers and students is developed to achieve objective; arise students' thirst towards STEM education. Being authors personal experience as a teacher, head teacher, trainer, administrator, meeting with peers, research scholars, trainee and trainer(s), there is less emphasis on trainings focusing national curriculum document guidelines specially in STEM education. Resultantly, teachers poorly portray their pedagogic potential among

students that results students deprived learning especially in the field of STEM education. The current research is an effort to measure the effect of curriculum base teaching methods used to implement STEM education in public sector primary schools of district Lahore, Punjab-Pakistan.

Research Questions

The researchers structured following research questions in this research

1. To what extent curriculum based teaching methods are affecting on promoting STEM education?
2. Is there association between teaching methods and STEM education?
3. To find out pattern of teaching methods used to implement STEM education?

Research Design and Methodology

A strategy used to guide researcher towards data collection and data analysis procedures for ending / completing research project. It grants direction that specifies collected information, its sources and ways of data collection (Coe et al., 2021; Jandric, 2021). The present study was quantitative leading to *ex-post-facto* design. The research design is mapping strategy used to guide researcher towards data collection and data analysis procedures for ending/completing research project. It grants directions that specifies collected information, its sources and ways of data collection (Knapper & Cropely, 2021; Walsh et al., 2021)

The Population and a Sample of Research

The population of the study consists of geographical location, age, gender, occupation, religious and ethnic group of the participants (Kelly et al., 2014). The larger group to which one hopes to apply the results is called the population (Gilbertson et al., 2022). Currently there are working 4,823 primary schools teachers; 2,072 females and 2,211 male in Tehsil, City, Cantt, Raiwind, Shalimar and Tehsil Model town where they are providing their services among students in promoting STEM education (Hassan et al., 2021; Pakistan District Education Ranking, 2016). The researchers selected only primary schools because, Government of Punjab implementing STEM education at primary level educational institutions. The sample is the representative part of entire population (Creswell, 2014) that consist of humans, objects, things, events or material that is being selected from entire population (Gay, et al., 2014; Singh, 2007). The sample of the research consisted 1,152 students selected from 64 schools; 18 students from each school of district Lahore where primary schools students were enrolled. The researchers applied randomly sampling technique; important technique of probability sample has fewer threats to collect the data from participants. The researchers selected male teachers because, in Pakistani educational institutions, female poorly cooperative and less provide their data for research purpose (Hassan, 2019; Hassan & Akbar, 2020), as the authors ensures ethical considerations to collect the data from the participants.

Instrumentation

The research instrument is crucial device used for data collection (McMillan & Schumacher, 2001; Mertler & Charles, 2005). The researchers administered one questionnaire having two parts. **Part A:** self-constructed questionnaire on teaching methods having 31-items categorized in 8-factors; lecture, discussion, demonstration, question answer, brainstorming, inquiry and cooperating teaching mode of 5-point Likert type options, **Part B:** after obtaining unrestricted and unfettered permission from the authors, the researchers adopted Nistor et al., (2018) scale on STEM education. The researchers ensured content validity of self-constructed questionnaire from English language, pedagogical and curriculum experts. Then, piloted a questionnaires on 100 respondents to ensure Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics; .858 and .798 respectively. After ensuring ethical considerations; informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, fairness, self-respect, no physical and psychological harm in case of respondents' volunteer participation, the researchers collected final data from the participants.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The researchers analyzed quantitative data in SPSS that underpins the concepts of statistical analysis (Cohen et al., 2011). The researchers applied regression analysis to measure the effect of national curriculum base teaching methods on promoting STEM education. The outputs of *Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r)* find out the relationship between dependent; STEM education and independent variables; teaching methods. Through applying mean and standard deviation, the researchers find out the maximum and minimum use of teaching methods use to implement STEM education.

Table 1 Effect of National Curriculum based Teaching Method on promoting STEM Education

Sr. No	Model	B	SE	β	t	p
	Constant (STEM)	548.79	3.717		147.656	.01
1	Lecture method	11.119	.504	.493	36.603	.01
2	Discussion method	10.241	.497	.113	.807	.00
3	Demonstration	.152	.253	.008	.602	.04
4	Question answer	.903	.274	.041	3.299	.01
5	Brainstorming	1.265	.237	.068	5.335	.60

6	Inquiry	.852	.225	.070	3.786	.09
7	Problem solving	4.117	.369	.184	11.144	.08
8	Cooperative	1.146	.344	.052	3.333	.01

Note: $R = .716^a$, $R^2 = .513$; $F(8, 1144) = 757.291$, $p < .05^a$, $Durbon-Watson = 1.25$

As established in Table 1, the researchers applied multiple linear regression to explore the effect of teaching methods on STEM education. Interpretation reflect formation of regression equation ($F(8, 1144) = 757.291$, $p < .01$ founding value of $R^2 .513$ with explaining 51.30% of increased variance were observed with standardized regression coefficient against lecture method ($\beta = .49$), question answer technique ($\beta = .04$), discussion method ($\beta = .113$), brainstorming ($\beta = .068$), demonstration method ($\beta = .008$), inquiry based method ($\beta = .07$), problem solving method ($\beta = .184$) and cooperative method ($\beta = .052$) respectively. Ensuring results of regression coefficient, the output of independent sample t-test revealed that lecture, $t(1150) = 36.603$, $p < .01$, question answer, $t(1150) = 3.299$, $p < .005$, discussion, $t(1150) = 0.807$, $p < .05$ and cooperative, $t(1150) = 3.333$, $p < .05$ were significant predictors while brainstorming, $t(1150) = 5.335$, $p > .01$, demonstration, $t(1150) = .602$, $p > .01$, inquiry, $t(1150) = 3.786$, $p < .01$ and problem solving, $t(1150) = 11.144$, $p < .01$ were found non-significant predictor on promoting STEM education. The students predicted success were equal to $548.79 + 11.119 + 0.093 + 10.24 + 1.265 + 0.152 + 0.85 + 4.117 + 1.146$ scores where teaching methods were measured in terms of teaching capabilities. It is concludes that STEM education was increased 29.792 by applying teaching methods.

Table 2 Correlation between Teaching Method and STEM Education

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1.Constant (STEM)	337.53	66.44									
2.Lecture method	11.85	2.93	.675**								
3.Question answer	15.89	2.92	.318**	.362**	-						
4.Discussion	15.11	3.68	.555**	.675**	.460**	-					
5.Brainstorming	14.98	3.57	.357**	.316**	.588**	.479**	-				
6.Demonstration	14.53	3.57	.465**	.521**	.480**	.639**	.530**	-			
7.Inquiry	22.21	5.47	.591**	.676**	.512**	.765**	.506**	.673**	-		
8.Problem solving	10.86	2.97	.572**	.573**	.461**	.694**	.532**	.636**	.775**	-	
9.Cooperative	11.11	3.04	.535**	.575**	.429**	.718**	.517**	.559**	.735**	.744**	-

As established in Table 2, the researchers run *Pearson Product Moment Correlation (r)* to find out relationship between teachers' different teaching methods with promoting STEM education. The results reveal large positive significant relationship between lecture method and STEM instructions ($r = .675^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), medium positive significant relationship between question answer and STEM discipline ($r = .362^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), medium positive significant relationship between discussion and STEM cultivation ($r = .460^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), medium positive significant relationship between brainstorming and STEM promoting ($r = .479^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), large positive significant relationship between demonstration and STEM learning ($r = .530^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), large positive significant relationship between inquiry and STEM coaching ($r = .673^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$), large positive significant relationship between problem solving and STEM implementation ($r = .775^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$) and were also reported large positive significant relationship between cooperative and STEM instructions ($r = .744^{**}$, $n = 1152$, $p < .01$). It is concluded that change in independent variable; teaching methods strongly influence on independent variable; promoting STEM education.

Figure 1 Pattern showing frequent usage of teaching methods for promoting STEM education

As delineated in Figure 1, the researchers applied descriptive statistics to find out maximum usage of

teaching methods in classrooms to implement STEM education. The interpretation reveals that teachers were ensuring maximum usage of lecture ($M = 22.206$, $SD = 5.471$), question answer ($M = 15.886$, $SD = 2.921$), discussion ($M = 15.110$, $SD = 3.684$), brainstorming ($M = 14.981$, $SD = 3.566$), demonstration ($M = 14.528$, $SD = 3.574$), cooperative ($M = 11.108$, $SD = 3.040$), inquiry ($M = 11.849$, $SD = 2.926$) and lastly use problem solving in promoting STEM education.

Discussion

Teaching methods play significant effects on students' diligence (Heckel et al., 2021), discipline (Dunne et al., 2021), mindfulness (González-García et al., 2021), self-confidence (Malureanu et al., 2021) and STEM education (Zendler et al., 2018). Teachers use variety of teaching methods both dull and intelligent student in various discipline for their active classroom participation. Lecture, discussion, demonstration, question answer, brainstorming, inquiry, problem solving and cooperative are important teaching methods (Crippen & Archambault, 2012; Government of Pakistan, 2006; Hassan & Akbar, 2020; Zendler et al., 2018) that are used to achieve instructional objectives (Omwirhiren & Ibrahim, 2016) in effective learning environment (McKeachie & Svinicki, 2006). The results of current research established that teachers teaching methods are good predictors that are promoting 51.30% consideration of STEM education among students that strongly support with the findings of the research structured by Zendler et al., (2018) whose findings assured that teachers teaching methods strengthen the concept of STEM education among students, especially in a conditions where teachers handle students in interdisciplinary and multi-perceptivity classes. Lecture method is considered as oral communication of thoughts, realities, conception and simplification of words. Teachers make maximum uses of lecture method in classrooms (Berry, 2008) especially STEM teaching (Hockicko et al., 2017) that align with the findings of current research whose findings established that teachers make use of lecture methods for students' classroom participation during STEM cultivation. Lecture is generally acknowledged and experienced method of instruction (Harman & Bich, 2010) that capable teacher to communicate on diverse feature (McKeachie & Svinicki, 2006). Discussion is important method of arousing students' hidden potential in classrooms. Classrooms discussions declare that students are agency of knowledge construction, large concern on questioning and make rationalization. Throughout discussion students have considerable authority of understanding for assessing the reliability of their peers' criticism (Rotenberg, 2005; Martínez-Clares & González-Morga, 2018) towards STEM education. The results of current research established that discussion play a significant role in cultivating STEM education that strongly correlate with the results of research structured by Breiner et al., (2012); Ortiz-Revilla et al., (2012) whose results established that STEM is used to

reside meta-disciplined subject or used to address unclear parameters during teaching-learning process. Demonstration put concrete effect on students' mental abilities. Teachers demonstrate the topic to support his/her explanations and then scaffold their learners' understanding. It is form of instructional approach that brazen out students "study how to study," encourage them to create their joint endeavor among peers to unearth response of actual problems (O'Donoghue et al., 2011). National curriculum document focuses on the demonstration of teachers' instructional strategies used to enhance students' rising wellbeing in acquiring multiplicity of subjects (Heck, 2009; Giridharan & Raju, 2016) that support with the result of current research and also align with the findings of other studies (Bell, 2016; Ejiwale, 2013) whose results reveals that use of discussion in STEM education make students critical thinker and problem solver in understanding real word application. Question answer is used for oral communication having strapping roots in students' reasoning (Mtunda & Safuli, 1997) and teachers used to enhance pupils' thoughts and understanding (Stolhmann et al., 2012). Teachers used question answer among students as a teaching instrument to gauge their understanding level (Njoroge et al., 2014) that congruent with the findings of current research and also align with the results of other studies (Gao et al., 2020; Radloff & Guzey, 2016). Literature supports that discussion effectively integrates into national curriculum to strengthen pedagogic competencies (Çepni, 2017;) focusing STEM aspects.

Brainstorming involves in the unstructured and unplanned contribution of thoughts. Teachers apply to encourage students' thoughts, ideas and polish hidden potential (Hu et al., 2017; Mohammad, 2016). The results of current research establish that teachers use brainstorming for cultivating STEM education, students' ground-breaking thoughts, build enthusiasm towards obtain information and to fortify their classroom participation (Malkawi & Smadi, 2018), that congruent with the findings of other studies (Voštinár et al., 2018; Aydin, 2020; Kulturel-Konak et al., 2011). Teachers apply this strategy to strengthen students' cognitive potential and intellectual abilities that revolves round formation of thought provoking directions toward successful mode of required achievements (Kittami, 2001). Inquiry use to intensify current-day subject understanding (Llewellyn, 2002), shape ideas with students prepared assumption and testing through experimentation and/or personal inspections (Muller & Haberman, 2008; Mäeots et al., 2008). The results of current research reveals that teachers use of inquiry put significant effect on enhancing STEM education. These findings strongly make parallel with the results of Lai (2018) whose results established that during inquiry teaching, the students showed their keen interest towards STEM teaching, and also support with the findings of other studies (Crippen & Archambault, 2012; Zhai, 2019). Problem solving is an important skill that assist individual's to logically define the problem, determine the reason of problem, identify, prioritize and select alternative solution ensuring its implementation (Kim et al., 2022). The findings of current research expose that teachers use problem solving to spread the knowledge of STEM education. The results support with the findings of other studies (Contente & Galvão, 2022; Lin et al., 2015). During inquiry, students collect their energies to achieve concerned task by focusing rules: understand notion & idea not willingly logical; identify the problem; analyze the problem; illustrate orderly list of details inferred from analyzing problem; prepare /construct objectives; gather information; then create & analysis recently collected data (Bagherpur et al., 2022; Koichu et al., 2022). Cooperative teaching is based on students and teachers; pillars of teaching learning process. Teachers work as instructors and motivators whereas students' performance seems in terms of better attainment (McMaster & Fuches, 2002; Nichols, 2002; Winston, 2002). The findings of current research reveal that teachers apply brainstorming during STEM teaching, which congruent with the findings of other researchers (Eckman et al., 2016; Hall & Miro, 2016; Smith et al., 2009). Teachers segregate students in diverse clusters to comprehend dilemma, task or any other instructive object, whereas teacher work as guider /catalyst (Thibaut et al., 2018). Teachers make maximum use of teaching methods to impend students' intellectual learning and to implement STEM education.

Conclusions

Lesson is less interested but appropriate use of teaching methods makes it attractive. Appropriate use of teaching methods makes students skilful, knowledgeable and fascinates teaching learning process. Pakistani teachers impart instructions among enrolled students focusing in national curriculum, 2006 based teaching methods to promote STEM education. On the basis of results, it is concluded that primary schools teachers were applying 47.70% less use of national curriculum based teaching methods for promoting STEM education. This massive percentage shows that teachers are poorly familiar with national curriculum document. National curriculum is to act as a foundation document for achieving goals of developing scientific literacy for students. This document aims to prepare students lifelong learning and engage students in inquiry base and problem solving situations. Furthermore, the results conclude that although lecture method is one-way traffic, however, teachers are still imparting STEM related instructions through maximum use of lecture methods and problem solving at minimum level. It is the alarming and painstaking situation for stakeholders. On the basis of results, it is recommended that Quaid-i-Azam Academy for Educational Development may arrange training for perspective and prospective teachers focusing content orient pedagogy, group activities, peer-learning,

modeling, mentoring, feedback and ensuring national curriculum document guidelines stated for implementing STEM education.

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